

FEMINISM, SOCIAL CHANGE AND THE FEMALE VOICES IN CONTEMPORARY NIGERIAN FICTION: A TEXTUAL STUDY OF ZAINAB ALKALI'S *THE STILLBORN*

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Abstract

Women, generally, are regarded as the weaker sex, a group that cannot be independent of the males, a group that is usually painted negatively in male-authored literary pieces and in fact, a group that must be seen but not heard and which is subject to the social whims and caprices of obnoxious patriarchal customs and traditions. This is rather appalling and because of it, female writers have taken it as a duty to redress and socially portray positively, the battered image of the womenfolk. In doing this, they present the female group as a make up of people who can and are decent, virtuous, pious, hard-working, independent, capable and responsible. As such, it is our strong belief that to fully understand and appreciate this fact, an indepth study of Zainab Alkali's *The Stillborn* is worth it. This is what is being attempted here.

Key words: Feminism, Social Change, Contemporary Nigerian Fiction

Introduction

Female dependency on the male is ageless, and consequent upon this phenomenon, the former has persistently struggled to achieve a reasonable degree of parity with her male counterpart. This struggle is borne out of the belief that she is oppressed and so is determined to end that oppression. It is upon this background that Zainab Alkali's *The Stillborn* is a novel worthy of detailed study.

Our scope in the study of Zainab Alkali's *The Stillborn* is woven around her dwelling on the consciousness of the Nigerian woman by making her aware of her second class status in northern Nigeria Muslim society as well as advocating a social change in attitude that gives rise to unnecessary sufferings in black women and sets out to correct the debased image of Nigerian women. Before going into the main study however, it is proper to have a peep into feminism as a term.

A critic, Liz Kelly defines feminism thus: "Feminism minimally speaking, is a belief that women are oppressed and a commitment to end that oppression"(163).

Feminism as a concept is rather protean and as such, it becomes difficult to arrive at a universally acceptable definition. It is in recognition of these variations in definition that Ruth Sheila observes:

Feminists do not agree among themselves on one all-inclusive and universally acceptable definition of the term feminism. Depending on one's political, sociological observations and goals; one's individual aspirations for womanhood and for humanity; one's understanding or interpretation of the word woman; and several other factors, the term feminism can mean different things and have variety of functions.(4)

In other words, Sheila observes here that feminism is multifarious so that the definition one gives to it will depend largely on the perspective from which one views it.

Some female writers look at feminism from a radical perspective and in that regard, advocate a thorough and complete equality with the male in all ramifications without a compromise, while some others are more liberal in their approach. The former category best describes some of Buchi Emecheta's novels while Ifeoma Okoye, Flora Nwapa and Zaynab Alkali whose work is being studied here, fall into the latter. Whichever way the term is viewed however, it is not unconnected with the liberation of womanhood; the group or gender which should be seen but never heard, from male chauvinism and social patriarchy.

The oppression of women is a universal phenomenon and because of this, the discourse is not devoid of a global dimension. Simone de Beauvoir in this respect observes: "The situation of women in the world is comparable to that of the American blacks. Both are being emancipated today from a like paternalism, and the former master class wishes to keep them in their place-that is second class citizen" (23).

The above observation is not only applicable to women in Europe and America but also to Nigerian women. In fact, Buchi Emecheta, one of Nigerian's feminist writers, derives the title of her second novel- *Second Class Citizen* from de Beauvoir's phrase.

We want to state, at this point, that it is appalling to note that social thought is not only male dominated but male-centred as well. The use of the word 'man', to represent humanity shows that the female is a derivation or subset of the male. This goes a long way to explain why more has been written about men than women and why the little that has even been written about women displays open bias. Flora Alexander points out in this respect: "Even today, when bookshops are amply stocked with literature by women and about them and with specialized materials from feminist publishing houses, it is still the case that women's writing receives less critical attention than is given to men's writing" (47).

Main Discussion

Coming to the core of this study, the literary genres happen to be one of the most effective media through which Nigerian female writers have voiced out, albeit vehemently, the need for women everywhere to rise up to the challenge of achieving a reasonable degree of parity with their male counterparts. Their perspective consists of taking interest in the lifestyles, activities and occupation of women both at home and in the society at large. From the foregoing, one can deduce that women desire a situation where they are valued, recognized and counted equal with the men in the society. Left to them, womanism is about valued autonomy for women as individuals and for them as a group. In this regard, they mean to develop in themselves and in their environment, the condition that will enable them control their own political, social, economic and personal destinies.

To buttress this, Sheila once again declares:

As feminists, we value and prize the fact of being woman as highly as we value the fact of being human. We do not accept the cultural images of women as incompetent, petty, irresponsible or weak. Rather, we affirm our capacities to be strong, capable, intelligent, successful. ethical human beings.(4)

Zainab Alkali's Social Vision: The Liberated Womanhood in *The Stillborn*

Female experience in Zaynab Alkali's novel owes its peculiarities to the predominantly Muslim society. The low status of Islamic women is evident in the repressive masculine dominance. These women have little or no say in the family where the father is the sole authority figure, nor in the sex-segregated community where the female gender is viewed as a 'tabula vasa'. The Islamic interpretation of the female sexuality forms the foundation for the tendency to keep women in purdah or "under the veil of Islam". The Qu'ran advocates the relegation of women to the private scene to perform the more "sacred and vital" roles of wife and mother. It is in this connection that women education is a rarity in the Northern part of Nigeria in the recent past.

Restricted to the domestic precincts, the Northern Nigerian Muslim woman undergoes a socialization process that celebrates the self-fulfilment of the male while undermining the autonomy of the female. This socialization process in one part prevents female social and political growth and on the other, is directed primarily towards the affirmation of eternal feminine virtues such as docility and chastity. It is against this background that Zaynab Alkali presents astonishing anguish of female realities and dreams in *The Stillborn*.

Zaynab Alkali's novel, *The Stillborn*, opens with the journey, which is an index of the author's unequivocal identification with the travelling woman. Li, the principal character, returns to the village after completing her primary education at a boarding school. She is thirteen years old and yearns to leave the suffocating atmosphere of a home; she calls it "worse than a prison" (3) presided over by her unloving and domineering father and assisted by an equally unpleasant deaf mother.

Li felt "trapped and unhappy... She missed the kind of life she had lived at the primary boarding school, free and gay" (3). Her father's compound is a microcosm of a patriarchal structure which represses female potentialities and wholeness. Kaka, in the light of this, judiciously observes: "Children shouldn't be caged...for if the cage got broken by accident or design, they would find the world too big to live in" (23).

Li is presented as the young girl, barely a teenager, who seeks to escape from the oppressive societal restrictions which seem to suffocate her. At quite an early age, she asserts herself and insists on doing even the simplest of things "without having someone breathing down on my neck demanding to know where I have been to" (3). There has been this driving force for emancipation in the life of the protagonist and in the personality of Li, Alkali presents women as not passive but assertive human beings. The boisterous Li, refusing to be caged in, stands counter-opposition to her self-effacing sister, Awa, who has thoroughly imbibed the Muslim dogma of female passivity.

Actually, there is an obvious lack of incentive for Li in the confines of the patriarchal household where slavery and monotony weaken the tempo of female aspiration. It is in the search for a more challenging tenor of that life that would put a woman on her mettle that Li migrates to the city and marries Habu Adams. Li's desire for gaiety and freedom suddenly seems achievable when she meets Habu at a village dance which to attend, she had to creep through an opening in the fence late in the night to avoid detection by her father. Habu, handsome and flamboyant, talks of leaving home soon to train as a doctor. It is pertinent to note here that in the course of their courtship and out of excitement, "Li walked happily, her feet barely touching the ground" (34). She is undoubtedly celebrating her independence from a repressive custom. Two years later, at 15, Li marries Habu just before he leaves for the city. The dream of escape and happiness fuelled in the last two years by her daring secret meetings with Habu in a village that disapproves of such things, is about to be fulfilled. She imagines what her future will be like: "The qualified doctor, the Grade 1 teacher, the big European house full of servants, the smooth body, the long silky hair... There was no end to the luxuries the city could offer" (57).

Li indeed becomes a Grade 1 teacher (15 years after) and even then, only as a result of the search for a balm for the wounds caused by splinters from her exploded dreams. Her first disappointment is that in the city, Habu has "become a salesman instead of a doctor" (57). In the second place, for four years, he has not fulfilled his promise to ask her to join him in the city. As such, fresh suitors, chief amongst them, the wealthy Alhaji Bature, pesters her: she has become an abandoned wife. When she is taken to Habu by a relative of his at last, "Li knew she had lost her man to the city" (70). Shortly after her arrival, Habu goes out and does not return until nightfall the day after, "drunken and violent" and it is in "the drunken intimacy" (70) that ensues, the first and the last in the city, that he impregnates her. Heavy with child and burdened with the bitter nightly knowledge that "the man lying on the other side of the room was a well dressed stranger who did not talk to a village woman" (70), Li wonders.

Finally, Li is urgently summoned to her dying father's side in the village but arrives to find that he had already been buried. Nevertheless, this loss strikes her with far less force than the living-death that marriage has turned out to be for her friend, Faku. Li, spending the night in Kano with Faku on her way to the village, finds her friend faring very badly as Garba's second wife.

Alkali does not mince words in presenting to her readers, through these female characters, the brutalizing and dehumanizing treatment women receive from a male dominated society. Women are seen to be like clothings anyone can acquire as much as one desires. Li encounters a failed marriage because her husband, Habu goes out with another woman. Garba too is a prototype of Li's husband, Habu. In fact, Garba is to Faku, his wife, what Habu is to Li. The two women have their hopes of running away from the prison and poverty of village life dashed to pieces as they are confronted with a helpless situation brought about by the patriarchal societal norms which give supremacy to the man. Alkali sets out to disprove this notion in the novel by presenting later that women are not merely pieces of wood that could be tossed here and there but are achievers even without their husbands.

Li's going to the village is a turning point for her: the point at which the spirit of independence she has shown from her childhood assumes the form of a stiff feminist determination to rely, not on a husband, but on herself for the fulfilment of her dreams. With this, Alkali drives home the feministic tendency which characterises the concept of feminism. The new woman presented in the persona, Li, has to face reality, prove to her husband and the whole world in general, that a woman can live a fulfilled life without her dependence on her husband. Looking critically at her own life and the trend of events, Li is convinced that her ideas of marriage are "still born" due to a lot of factors that she could hardly control but which does not stop her from starting off on a new slate of dreams even when it appears as if everything has come crashing down her feet.

As a result of the foregoing, and realizing that her father's house needs some touching up, and knowing the onus falls on her, she decides to undertake some training that will provide her with the means to meet up with her responsibilities. She is armed with virtue and determination and successfully resists the advances of fresh suitors and completes her studies at teachers' college. As a determined woman, she makes deliberate efforts to regaining her self-esteem, particularly through self-education. Awa perceiving this incredible change in her sister, thoughtfully reflects:

This wasn't the sister she was used to, impetuous and critical of people. This was a different Li, tolerant and understanding. What had brought about this change? The emotional hardships she went through- the city?... Li had, no doubt, matured and in the process of maturing, had become a better person with a finer soul. (94)

Rather than remaining despondent in the circumstance Li finds herself, as females are sometimes presented in most male-authored novels, Alkali, in the person of Li, presents women as resilient and courageous people in the face of adverse situations.

To buttress the foregoing, Awa tells Li when their grandfather dies that "The mourners are outside and waiting for you. You are the man of the house now" (101). And in fact, we see Li assuming this lofty role through the narrator commenting "Li sat still in the armchair and crossed her elegant legs" (101). What Alkali tries in this circumstance to declare to her readers, is that their being females does not in any way mean that they can not "man" the house. Li, is in fact, an achiever, a successful single lady who has single-handedly climbed the ladder of success without the support

of her husband. The narrator makes this obvious: "At last she had accomplished her ambitions. She was a successful teacher and an owner of a huge modern and enviable building" (101). What else does she want?

Faku too is another victim of male dominance in patriarchal society who proved herself in the end, a liberated woman. She is subjugated and under utter repression as her husband's first wife 'rules the house' and like her childhood friend, Li, decides to go out of her way to seek fulfilment for her life, following a dilapidated marriage. This action of Faku's further foregrounds vehemently, Alkali's message of female emancipation and quest for fulfilment on their own. Faku is like Dora in Flora Nwapa's *Women Are Different* who leaves her husband to acquire strength and economic independence so as to be able to dictate the pace of her life. In this regard, she asserts herself. The narrator, in recognition of this, comments on the exploits of Faku:

Li had listened spellbound to Faku's account of her experiences in various cities after finding the courage to leave Garbage. For years, Faku had drifted without a proper sense of direction. Then, three years ago, she had been befriended by a kind, elderly woman who interested herself in social welfare work. Now Faku was on the way to becoming a social welfare worker herself. Li felt happy for her friend who had found fulfilment at last. (102)

Judging from the above, one would think that Alkali is clearly writing from a feminist point of view which advocates a total separation between males and females. However, in a dramatically ironic reversal of events, which undercuts the new position of the sophisticated and independent woman, Li decides to return to her irresponsible husband even after ten years of separation. As it were, something seems to be lacking in Li's life in spite of her achievement. The narrator observes:

Li ought to have felt fulfilled, but instead she felt empty. It wasn't just the emptiness of bereavement, but an emptiness that went beyond that. For ten years she had struggled towards certain goals. Now, having accomplished these goals, she wished there was something else to struggle for. For that was the only way life could be meaningful. (102)

In short, Li discovers that the bond that has tied her only daughter to her father, Habu Adams, is not ruptured and the missing thing in her is reunion with her husband. The narrator, once again, narrates: "And in spite of everything, in the soft cradle of her heart, there was another baby forming. This time, Li was determined the baby would not be stillborn" (105). Awa shakes her head in thought and asks:

"You are going back to him?"

"Yes".

"Why, Li? The man is lame", said the sister.

"We are all lame, daughter-of-my-mother. But this is no time to crawl. It is time to learn to walk again". (105)

This, we must note, is ironical. Up to this climatic moment, we recognize Li's patently positive qualities and the true feminist can relate with her at that positive level. Fortunately or unfortunately, there is a serious contradiction, indeed self-negation in Li at this moment in the sense that having learnt to lead an independent and fulfilled life, Li still takes her faithless husband back when he returns to her, broken and lame. This situation is a reminiscence of a similar event in Elechi Amadi's *Estrangement*; despite their newfound economic independence and freedom from men's domination as a result of education and business opportunities, Alee and Christie still hunger after male protection and a child respectively.

Conclusion

In this study, we have been able to examine Zaynab Alkali's *The Stillborn* under the topic "Feminism, Social Change and the Female Voices in Contemporary Nigerian Fiction: A Study of Zaynab Alkali's *The Stillborn*" as it relates to the secondary position women have been subjected to in a male-dominated society, and how the female novelists like Alkali, have taken it upon themselves to reverse this trend by presenting the making of an emancipated woman.

We have also seen how the protagonist, Li in the text under study, ends up in a reunion with her husband. One might want to ask whether Alkali is saying that women cannot stand on their own; or cannot do without the men. It does not really appear so. Rather, they are implying, according to Ernest Emenyonu, that "Black feminists, unlike white feminists, eschew bitterness in their confrontation and relationship with men. An integral part of the writer's vision is the mutual interdependence that can exist between man and woman in a union or association of equals" (34).

Nevertheless, it is pertinent to point out that Nigerian female novelists have, to a large extent, recreated the social experience of their people. Women's social experience forms an integral part of the entire national social experience which they deliberately create. Thus, they present women as well educated, self-reliant, economically independent, confident, ambitious, aggressive and morally sound. Her intention is to create appropriate awareness aimed at putting an end to the subjection and oppression of womanhood.

Reuben Abati in his article titled "Women in Transition", commented on the extent to which women have been reduced. Abati opines:

Within the last decade, development scholars across the continent have had to tackle the problem of women. Based on concerted research, the conclusion has long been reached that women are decentered, denatured subspecies of humanity, harassed by culture, intimidated by politics and subsumed under patrilineal and patriarchal structure which pampers male ego (8).

Despite this, we have seen in this study, Li and Faku who have asserted themselves and left behind them, a monument of power, glory and deep respect.

It is pertinent to state here that as much as these female writers desire equality, equity and emancipation, we have also seen in this work that they do not on strict terms advocate for total separation between the husband and his wife. Rather, they advocate partnership of mutual interest, understanding and respect. It is on this basis that an obvious dichotomy is drawn between American feminists and African (Nigerian in particular) feminists or womanists. These female writers are aimed at revamping the degenerating image of womanhood in the society. Hence, we find in their novels, examples of successful, hardworking career women like lawyers, journalists, businesswomen, teachers, doctors, amongst others.

The success so far achieved by women in their quest for female liberation can be attributed to their educational attainments. In fact, Western education has been a significant factor that has revolutionized the life of Nigerian women and as such, feminist writers vehemently advocate for education for women. For instance, in Nigeria today, women seem to be getting a better deal as seen in the formulation of favourable policies by the Federal Government which cater for the interests of women. The Federal Government policy on education favours women as there are more Federal Government Colleges for girls than for boys. Also, in the tertiary institutions, we now have more female students than ever before, in almost all disciplines.

Therefore, we want to conclusively state that if this trend of enlightenment continues amongst the women, their status in the society and especially in Nigeria, will take a drastic positive turn for the better in the nearest future

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